

1 Supplementary Materials for

2 3 **The Evolution of Female-Biased Genital Diversity in Bedbugs (Cimicidae)**

4 5 **This file includes:**

6
7 Supplementary Text

8 Figs. S1 to S6

9 Tables S1 to S8

10 11 12 **Supplementary Methods**

13 14 **Variability in the male intromission site**

15 We used observations from our laboratory protocols of 15 years of work with *Cimex lectularius*.
16 We counted the number of copulations that were placed outside the intromission site and related
17 this to the approximately 35,000 copulations involving ca. 7,000 females and ca. 15,000 males
18 that had been observed or video-recorded in our laboratory. For *Afrocmex constrictus* we re-
19 visited the scoring sheet used to examine the mating rate (Reinhardt et al. 2007) and counted
20 the number of females with mating scars outside the spermalege. Dried and cleared museum
21 material of two *Aphrania* species (Senckenberg Museum in Frankfurt/ Main (Germany) and
22 *Cacodmus vicinus* (The Steinhardt Museum of Natural History, Israel National Center for
23 Biodiversity Studies at Tel Aviv University) were examined for melanised mating scars inside
24 and outside the spermalege area.

25 26 **Supplementary Discussion**

27 28 **Cimicid Biogeography**

29 Bayesian analysis of geographic origins revealed the most recent common ancestor of the
30 Cimicidae (Fig. S5, node 69) was living in the Nearctic when it started to diverge about 100
31 MYA (probability 0.27). An alternative origin of Nearctic, Africa and/or Neotropics was almost
32 equally probable (0.25). The statistical uncertainty in the DIVA analysis (Yu et al. 2015; Yu et
33 al. 2020) requires caution when interpreting the geographical trajectories, particularly of the
34 oldest clades of the group. After the break-up of Pangaea, which started around 195 MYA
35 (Torsvik and Cocks 2013) there was already some separation between Laurentia (including
36 Nearctic) and Gondwana in the south, suggesting that the lineage leading to *Afrocmex* could
37 have a Gondwanan origin when it split from its sister clade about 90 MYA. The early separation
38 of two main clades (node 67), gave one lineage of predominantly southern species
39 (Neotropical/Africa/ Saharo-Arabian) (node 66) and another with Nearctic, Eurasian and
40 Oriental clades (node 49). Eurasian Cimicidae were present as late as about 48 MYA in a shared
41 lineage with a Nearctic and Oriental region that splits into an Oriental–Eurasian clade (node
42 44) and a Palaeartic–Nearctic clade (node 48). Interestingly, this split appears to have happened
43 after the collision of India with the Eurasian continent. The African and Saharo-Arabian regions
44 appear to have experienced a vicariance event ca 65 MYA (node 59), following separation from
45 the Americas (node 66).

46 47 **Interpretation of character co-variance evolution**

48 Our Bayesian analysis indicated modest covariance between female and male character state
49 changes (Fig. S4, Table S4). However, establishing female genitalia as a causal driver of the
50 change in male genitalia (or vice versa) is, of course, difficult in phylogenetic analyses, which
51 essentially are correlations. In addition, joint state changes may represent independent
52 synapomorphies on the same node. If so, they may represent pseudo-replication (Maddison and

53 FitzJohn 2015). Finally, the chronological order of some events on the same branch may not be
54 resolved. Note also that none of our analyses of sexual co-variation reached a Bayes Factor >10
55 (Tables S4, S5) and the interpretations are based on substantial but overall still not decisive
56 statistical effects.

57 The interpretation of character evolution also affects the estimates of evolutionary rates.
58 We mapped character change with parsimony (Figs 2, S2), which assumes homogenous rates
59 of change over the tree and potentially may be smoothing over actual evolutionary transitions
60 and leave them undetected (Currie and Meade 2014). With a Bayesian model that allows for
61 variable rates of state transitions we found rates were usually higher in females than in males.

62 With a Bayesian analysis that models character changes with heterogeneous rates, character
63 changes that appear as joint events with parsimony reconstruction may potentially become
64 displaced to different branches of the tree. In order to maintain the notion that the pair is still
65 causally associated in coevolution one has to assume a delayed evolutionary response, i.e.
66 beyond speciation. For example, the extension of paramere length at node 66 followed by a
67 spermalege shift at node 59 would be a delayed response. The question would be, therefore, if
68 the male-imposed damage on female fitness is small enough to prevent extinction without
69 female responses at node 66, why would it be large enough to continue to impose selection for
70 millions of years until after speciation at node 59? Similarly, a change in spermalege position
71 at node 58 may have stimulated the evolution of a shorter paramere at node 55. However, such
72 cases were rare in our data set and we did not observe any global directional patterns. We
73 conclude that such delayed responses are unlikely a driving factor in the coevolution of both
74 sexes (at least for the characters studied here).

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76 **Additional Supplementary References**

77

78 Currie, T. E., and A. Meade. 2014. Keeping yourself updated: Bayesian approaches in
79 phylogenetic comparative methods with a focus on Markov chain models of discrete character
80 evolution. In: *Modern phylogenetic comparative methods and their application in*
81 *evolutionary biology* (ed. L. Z. Garamszegi,). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg,
82 263–286.

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84 Schuh, R. T., and C. Weirauch. 2020. *True Bugs of the World (Hemiptera: Heteroptera):*
85 *Classification and Natural History.*

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87 Figure S1. Morphological variation in the copulatory organs of bedbug genera
 88 (Cimicidae). The spermalege position (second panel from the left) is indicated by dots,
 89 the colour of which corresponds to the segment number indicated in Fig. 1. Interspecific
 90 variation in the intromittent organs of male bedbugs was obtained from photographs
 91 (third panel) and, for comparison, redrawn from the classic source (Usinger 1966) (fourth
 92 panel). An asterisk (*) represents an initial source of disagreement between photograph
 93 and drawing that was settled based on our own material (see text). Like the cimicid's
 94 putative sister group, the Polycetenidae (Schuh and Weirauch 2020), all intromittent
 95 organs are i) laterally convoluted hypodermic needle-like organs, ii) derived parameres,
 96 iii) left asymmetric, iv) situated on the ventral side of the ninth segment and v) shorter
 97 than the length of two segments. The dotted circle in *Primicimex* that lacks a spermalege,
 98 indicates the penetration area (see Usinger 1966).
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GENUS	SPERMALEGE POSITION		PARAMERE SHAPE & SIZE		
	dorsal	ventral	this study	Redrawn from Usinger	Category Shape/size
<i>Primicimex</i>					1/2
<i>Bucimex</i>					1/*2
<i>Afrocimex</i>					1/2
<i>Paracimex</i>					4/1
<i>Cimex</i>					1/2
<i>Leptocimex</i>					3/3
<i>Stricticimex</i>			no current material		4/1
<i>Cacodmus</i>					1/4
<i>Aphrania</i>					1/2
<i>Synxenoderus</i>					2/1
<i>Haematosiphon</i>			no current material		2/1
<i>Psitticimex</i>					4/*3
<i>Acanthocrios</i>					4/2

segments

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- 3-4
- 4-5
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- 6-7
- unknown

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105 **Figure S2. Evolution of length and shape of the male copulatory organ (paramere) in**
 106 **bedbugs. The paramere of all cimicids is left asymmetric and varies in length from being**
 107 **much shorter than its carrying segment 9 to reaching beyond segment 8 (character states**
 108 **are colour coded, right tree). It also varies in shape from being convex to straight, s-**
 109 **shaped or strongly concave (when viewed proximally) (character states are colour coded,**
 110 **left tree). Data are taken from (Usinger 1966) and own observations (Table S2). Ancestral**
 111 **character states were reconstructed with parsimony in PAUP (Swofford 2003) on a**
 112 **Bayesian consensus tree (Roth et al. 2019).**

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Figure S3a. Ancestral character state reconstruction for the segmental location of the spermalege, using MrBayes (with MBASR). State and colour codes on top. Sector size on node marks (numbered) corresponds to the probability of states at the node. Black numbers on branches indicate probable transitions to single state. Scale is time in million years.

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S3b. Ancestral character state reconstruction for the vertical position of the spermalege, using MrBayes (with MBASR). State and colour codes on top. Sector size on node marks (numbered) corresponds to the probability of states at the node. Black numbers on branches indicate probable transitions to single state. Scale is time in million years.

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Figure S3c. Ancestral character state reconstruction for the paramere shape, using MrBayes (with MBASR). State and colour codes on top. Sector size on node marks (numbered) corresponds to the probability of states at the node. Black numbers on branches indicate probable transitions to single state. Scale is time in million years.

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 137 **Figure S3d.** Ancestral character state reconstruction for the paramere length, using MrBayes
 138 (with MBASR). State and colour codes on top. Sector size on node marks (numbered)
 139 corresponds to the probability of states at the node. Black numbers on branches indicate
 140 probable transitions to single state. Scale is time in million years.
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Figure S4. Number and position of evolutionary changes in male (blue) and female (red) genital structures in the bedbug family (Cimicidae) as inferred from Bayesian reconstruction. Vertical double arrows mark spermalege changes along the segmental axis, horizontal double arrows along the left-middle-right axis (cf. Figs. 1, S3a,b). Evolutionary changes in paramere length are denoted by blue upright triangles, in paramere shape by blue sickle shapes (cf. figure S3c,d). Asterisks mark branches with male or female character changes that are accompanied by geographic (green) or by host changes (purple). Node IDs are in grey and are only shown if there were evolutionary changes. Two small red asterisks next to Node ID denote a change across two female characters states.

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Figure S5. Reconstructed biogeography of the bedbug family (Cimicidae). Historical biogeography of Cimicidae estimated with RASP v.4 (Yu et al. 2015; Yu et al. 2020) using the DIVA-like model, random samples from a set of Bayesian trees, a dated phylogenetic consensus tree, and the present occurrences of the studied species in coded geographic regions. Oriental Region (A), Eurasia (B), Nearctic (C), Neotropical (D), Africa (south of Sahara) (E), Oriental-Malaysia (F), Saharo-Arabian (G). A time stratified area exchange matrix with periods, 0-6.6, 6.6-13.1, 13.1-26.2, 26.2-52.3, 52.3-104.5 MYA was used as weak constraints (0.5) on exchange between Eurasia and the Neotropics (B to D) and Neotropics and Malaysia (D to F) between 6.6 to 13.1 million years ago. The width of sectors surrounding nodes signify probabilities for each of the possible ancestral areas of the node.

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Figure S6. Phylogram showing relative evolutionary rates of genital morphology in male (black) and female (yellow). Genital characters were estimated with Bayesian reverse jump stepping stone MCMC from terminal branch distribution of character states and topology constrained on a dated phylogenetic tree (Roth et al. 2019). Branch lengths on both trees were estimated with the variable rates multistate character model in BayesTraits (Pagel et al. 2004). To compare evolutionary rates in males and females we scaled the trees to the same tree depth. Rates could thus be calculated by dividing branch lengths on the respective branch lengths from the chronogram (see Fig. 3).

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Table S1. Summary of the genital traits of the Cimicidae species investigated in this study. Spermalege (abdominal) segment number, spermalege position on the abdomen and paramere shapes were given, whereby straight includes cases of nearly straight. Paramere lengths were classified as lengths relative to abdomen segments: 1 - not at all reaching the anterior margin of the segment IX, 2 - reaching the anterior margin of segment IX, 3 - extending well into segment VIII, 4 - extending well beyond segment VIII. Note that there was no ambiguity in classifying spermalege position and segment number between two observers and Usinger 1966, while five ambiguities (indicated by *) in paramere length or shape between Usinger 1966 and two observers were resolved based on our own material. Sources were abbreviated as follows: NL – Naturalis Leiden, O – own material (Roth et al. 2019), U – Usinger 1966, Ua – Ueshima 1968a, Ub – Ueshima 1968b. For *Primicimex cavernis*, which lacks a spermalege, the intromission site is given.

Species	Spermalege Segment	Spermalege Position	Source	Paramere Shape	Paramere Length	Source
<i>Afrocimex constrictus</i>	2-4	left	U	convex	2	O, U*
<i>Paracimex setosus</i>	5	mid-right	U	straight	1	NL
<i>Paracimex borneensis</i>	5	middle	U	straight	2	O, U, Ub
<i>Paracimex avium</i>	5	middle	U	straight	2	NL, U, Ub
<i>Paracimex cf. chaeturus</i>	5	middle	Ua	convex	1	O, Ub
<i>Cimex hirundinis</i>	6	right	U	convex	2	O, U
<i>Cimex vicarius</i>	6	right	U	convex	2	O, U
<i>Leptocimex duplicatus</i>	5-6	left & right	U	strongly concave	4	O, U
<i>Aphrania elongata</i>	5-6	middle	U	convex	4	O, U
<i>Cacodmus cf. sparsilis</i>	6	left	U	convex	4	U
<i>Stricticimex cf. namru</i>	3-4	right	U	concave	2	U
<i>Cacodmus vicinus</i>	6	left	U	convex	3	O, U
<i>Aphrania recta</i>	unknown	left	U	convex	2	O, U
<i>Aphrania barys</i>	unknown	unknown	U	s-shaped	2	O, U*
<i>Cacodmus villosus</i>	6	left	U	convex	3	O, U*
<i>Cacodmus cf. villosus</i>	6	left	U	convex	3	O, U
<i>Cimex hemipterus</i>	6	right	U	convex	2	O, U
<i>Ornithocoris pallidus</i>	6-7	mid-right	U	concave	2	O, U
<i>Haematosiphon inodorus</i>	6-7	middle	U	concave	2	O, U
<i>Acanthocrios furnarii</i>	6-7	right	U	straight	2	O, U
<i>Psitticimex uritui</i>	6	middle	U	straight	3	O
<i>Synxenodorus comosus</i>	6-7	right	U	concave	2	O, U*
<i>Cyanolicimex patagonicus</i>	5-6	middle	U	straight	1	O, U
<i>Cimexospis nyctalis</i>	5-6	mid-right	U	straight	2	O, U
<i>Cimex sp.</i>	6	right	U	convex	2	O, U
<i>Cimex pipistrelli gr.</i>	6	right	U	convex	2	O, U
<i>Cimex lectularius</i>	6	right	U	convex	2	O, U
<i>Cimex cf. emarginatus</i>	6	right	U	convex	2	O, U
<i>Primicimex cavernis</i>	5-6	left	U	convex	2	O, U*
<i>Bucimex chilensis</i>	4-5	right	U	convex	2	O, U
<i>Cimex latipennis</i>	6	right	U	convex	2	O, U
<i>Cimex antennatus</i>	6	right	U	convex	1	O, U
<i>Cimex adjunctus</i>	6	right	U	convex	2	O, U

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Table S2. Overview of the observed trait changes per branch in the Cimicidae in relation to node and node age (in million years, MYA). Paramere and spermalege changes are based on a parsimony ancestor character analysis. For geographic change see Material and Methods and Figure S5. Host changes were classified according to Roth et al. 2019. Equally parsimonious, alternative scenarios are provided in brackets and indicated with an asterisk* (also see Fig. 2).

Node ID	Node age (MYA)	Number of paramere changes			Number of spermalege changes			Spermalege change across two character states?	Geographic change	Branch with host change
			Change on upper branch	Change on lower branch (* alternative)		Change on upper branch	Change on lower branch (* alternative)		D - Dispersal V - Vicariance (*path probability>0.6)	
36	24.5	0			2		L to R, 5/6 to 4/5	1	V*	
37	2.0	0			0			0		lower
38	6.0	0			0			0		
39	12.0	0			0			0	V*	lower
40	15.0	0			0			0	D, V*	
41	0.5	0			0			0		
42	0.7	1 or 2 (see node 43)	Short→medium	(convex→straight*)	1		M to R/M	0		
43	14.0	0 or 1 (see node 42)		(convex→straight*)	0 or 1(see node 44)		(R to M*)	0	V*	
44	36.0	1		medium→short	1 or 2 (see node 43)		6 to 5, (R to M*)	1	D	
45	10.0	0			0			0		lower
46	10.0	1	medium→short		0			0		
47	27.0	0			0			0		
48	42.0	0			0			0	V*	
49	48.0	0			0			0	D, V	upper

50	6.0	0			0			0		
51	7.0	0			0			0		
52	19.0	2	concave→strongly concave	extra long→medium	2	R to L/R	5/6 to 3/4	1		upper
53	n.d.	0			0			0		
54	9.0	0			0			0	V*	
55	18.0	1		extra-long→long	0			0	D*	
56	n.d.	1	convex→straight		0			0		
57	34.0	1	(extra- long→medium*)	(extra- long→medium*)	1	L to M		0		
58	45.0	0			1	5/6 to 6		0		
59	65.0	1	convex→concave		1		R to L	1	V*	
60	21.0	2	medium→long	straight→concave	1	6/7 to 6		0	V*	lower
61	11.0	1	straight→concave		1		M/R to R	0		upper
62	17.0	0			1		6/7 to 5/6	1	V*	
63	27.0	0			1		M to M/R	0	D*	
64	38.0	1		straight→concave	1		M to R	0		
65	51.0	1	medium→short		1		5/6 to 6/7	1	V*	
66	72.0	2	medium→extra long	convex→straight	1		R to M	0	D, V	lower
67	78.0	0			1	5/6 to 6		0	D	
68	89.0	0			2	5/6 to 2-4	L to R	1	V	
69	104.0	0			0			0	D	

Table S3: Comparison of the number of reconstructed character changes using Parsimony or Bayesian Ancestral State Analysis (BACA). Changes of two types of characters per sex were counted separately (see Figures 1, 2, Table S2). Buridan's ass refers to a reconstruction of the prediction by the Buridan's ass process (see text for details).

Character Change	Parsimony	BACA
Spermalege segmental axis	9	13
Spermalege left-middle axis	11	14
Paramere shape	8	8
Paramere size	9	10
Simultaneous changes Spermalege -Paramere	6 (up to 8)	7 or 10
Simultaneous changes Spermalege -Geography	7 (or 8)	9
Simultaneous changes Spermalege -host	2	2
Simultaneous changes Paramere-Geography	3 (or 4)	2
Simultaneous changes Paramere-host	4	5
Buridan's ass	0	0
Simultaneous change Spermalege -Paramere with geography	2 (or 3)	1
Simultaneous change Spermalege -Paramere with host	2	1 or 2

Table S4. Pairwise comparison of character covariation between male and female genitalia characters using a homogenous rates model versus a covarion model. Columns "No covariation" and "covariation" give marginal log likelihood values for the models that characters a) vary by a homogenous rate ("No covariation") or b) covary with characters of the other sex. The Bayes Factor BF compares the two hypotheses, logBF 2-6 indicates positive, 6-10 strong, and >10 very strong evidence against the null hypothesis of no covariation (Meade and Pagel 2022).

	Spermalege R/L position		
	No covariation	covariation	Log BF
Spermalege segment	-81.7437	-79.5079	4.4716
	Male paramere shape		
Spermalege segment	-72.7682	-70.4325	4.6714
Spermalege R/L position	-78.2945	-74.6234	7.3422
	Male paramere length		
Spermalege segment	-78.092024	-76.277937	3.6282
Spermalege R/L position	-76.660520	-74.667462	3.9860
Male paramere shape	-72.591242	-69.090002	7.0024

Table S5. Pairwise comparison of character covariation between male and female genitalia characters and geographical and host variation a homogenous rates model versus a covarion model. Columns "No covariation" and "covariation" give marginal log likelihood values for the models that characters vary at a homogenous rate ("No covariation") or depending how other factors vary (covariation). The Bayes Factor BF compares the two hypotheses, whereby $\log BF < 2$ indicates weak, 2-6 positive, 6-10 strong, and > 10 very strong evidence against the null hypothesis of no covariation (Meade and Pagel 2022).

		No covariation	covariation	Log BF
Host	Geography	-84.9701	-86.5964	-3.25
	Host			
Spermalege segment	Geography	-86.1142	-87.7334	-3.239
	Host	-73.8444	-75.4443	3.2
Spermalege R/L	Geography	-95.6506	-93.8249	3.651
	Host	-76.802	-81.4881	9.372
Spermalege segment+R/L	Geography	-67.2217	-64.6020	5.239
	Host	n.a.	n.a.	
Male paramere length	Geography	-87.152228	-85.44337	3.4177
	Host	-74.828215	-70.950607	7.7553
Male paramere shape	Geography	-84.945	-82.3595	5.171
	Host	-65.2271	-67.094	3.734

Table S6. Evolutionary rates (trait changes over time) in the Cimicidae. Linear regression analyses for phenotypic changes over evolutionary time for individual subfamilies, separately given for all nodes and for terminal taxa. The female:male (F:M) ratio is the ratio of the regression slopes. Note that phenotypic changes are scaled for the different number of characters states in males and females.

Family Cimicidae:

All nodes (N=69)	Female	$y = 0.8978x - 1.7823$	$R^2 = 0.8733$
	Male	$y = 0.5684x + 1.9792$	$R^2 = 0.7063$
	Ratio F:M	1.58	
Terminal taxa (N=35)	Female	$y = 0.8835x - 1.4262$	$R^2 = 0.9086$
	Male	$y = 0.5485x + 2.5771$	$R^2 = 0.6971$
	Ratio F:M	1.61	
Oldest nodes (N=5)	Female	$y = 0.8417x + 5.7922$	$R^2 = 0.9656$
	Males	$y = 0.4438x - 0.3666$	$R^2 = 0.9852$
	Ratio F:M	1.89	

Subfamily Haematosiphoninae:

All nodes (N=13)	Females	$y = 0.8871x - 0.5529$	$R^2 = 0.9218$
	Males	$y = 0.6811x + 1.7893$	$R^2 = 0.9542$
	Ratio F:M	1.3	
Terminal taxa (N=7)	Females	$y = 0.6434x + 2.9639$	$R^2 = 0.9400$
	Males	$y = 0.8523x + 0.8651$	$R^2 = 0.8863$
	Ratio F:M	0.75	

Subfamily Cacodminae

All nodes (N=21)	Females	$y = 1.0046x - 2.0244$	$R^2 = 0.9227$
	Males	$y = 1.0324x - 1.3722$	$R^2 = 0.8956$
	Ratio F:M	0.97	
Terminal taxa (N=11)	Females	$y = 1.0036x - 1.5264$	$R^2 = 0.8812$
	Males	$y = 0.9342x + 0.1927$	$R^2 = 0.7612$
	Ratio F:M	0.93	

Subfamily Cimicinae

All nodes (N=27)	Females	$y = 0.6919x - 1.1046$	$R^2 = 0.469$
	Males	$y = 0.4998x + 0.4436$	$R^2 = 0.7272$
	Ratio F:M	1.38	
Terminal taxa (N=14)	Females	$y = 0.4141x + 0.3899$	$R^2 = 0.9647$
	Males	$y = 0.4996x + 0.4029$	$R^2 = 0.8196$
	Ratio F:M	1.21	

Table S7. Expected and observed simultaneous changes between male and female traits. Expected probabilities of simultaneous changes (co-occurrence) were calculated as the product of the frequencies of the two traits, given the total of 68 branches. Chi square values for non-zero observations were calculated using the Yates correction and significance indicated for 1 d.f. Individual character changes were 11 for Right/Left (R/L) position and 9 for segmental changes in female genitalia, and 9 change in paramere length and 8 in paramere shape for males.

spermalege character	paramere character	co-occurring P1 * P2	expected changes	observed changes	Chi square (Yates correction)
R/L position	Shape	$0.162 * 0.118 = 0.019$	1.29	4 (or 5)	3.786 (or 7.988) p = 0.051 (or 0.005)
R/L position	Length	$0.162 * 0.132 = 0.021$	1.43	0 (or 1)	
Segment	Shape	$0.132 * 0.118 = 0.016$	1.08	0	
Segment	Length	$0.132 * 0.132 = 0.017$	1.16	3	1.548
dorsal-ventral	Shape	$0.029 * 0.118 = 0.003$	0.20	0	
dorsal-ventral	Length	$0.029 * 0.132 = 0.004$	0.27	0	

Table S8. Variability in the copulatory intromission site in different cimicid species. Based on the presence of melanised copulatory scars (first four species), or by direct observation (*C. lectularius*) the proportion of females was estimated that received intromissions outside the spermalege. The data for *Afro cimex constrictus* are from cave populations in Kenya and female morphs were described in detail in Reinhardt et al. (2007). Note that *A. constrictus* performs male-male inseminations. "Proportion of females" refers to the proportion of females receiving at least one mating outside their copulatory organ, the number of females sampled is given in brackets, the average number of matings/individual outside the copulatory organ is gynomorph females: 3.0, andromorph-2 females: 2.8, andromorph-3 females: 3.2, males: 0.7. Note that one ancestral species (*Primicimex*) (Usinger 1966) has a wide scatter in the intromission site in the absence of a spermalege.

Species	Morph/ sex	Site	Proportion of females (N females)
<i>Afro cimex constrictus</i>	Gynomorph female	Kenya, Kitum cave	57% (7)
		Kenya, Makingeni cave	71% (7)
		Kenya, Ngwarisha cave	85% (39)
	Andromorph female 2	Kenya, Makingeni cave	83% (18)
	Andromorph female 3	Kenya, Makingeni cave	83% (18)
	Females total		84% (85)
	Male	Kenya, Kitum cave	0% (23)
		Kenya, Makingeni cave	43% (93)
		Kenya, Ngwarisha cave	7% (60)
	Males total		38% (176)
<i>Aphrania vishnou</i>	females	Malaysia, Thailand	50% (2)
<i>Aphrania elongata</i>	females	Burkina Faso (N=6), Sudan (N=9)	12% (17)
<i>Cacodmus vicinus</i>	females	Israel, 4 localities	6.6 % (15)
<i>Cimex lectularius</i>	females	Laboratory population	0.02% (~35,000)